

CS Track Press Release

17 March 2020

CS Track - systematically investigating Citizen Science

CS Track is a new European research project which will broaden our knowledge about Citizen Science and the impact Citizen Science activities can have in order to maximise their potential benefit on individual citizens, organisations, and society at large.

Citizen science varies greatly and there appears to be little agreement about the forms it can take, what activities are called citizen science? how are citizen science projects conducted? what are their societal, economic, educational and scientific effects? who participates in such projects? how and why? The list goes on.... In CS Track our research team plan to narrow this considerable knowledge gap by conducting research on these issues and others across a broad range of projects in the European Union, Associated Countries and beyond.

CS Track is a 3 year project funded by the European Commission which brings together partners from 7 countries who will investigate a large and diverse set of Citizen Science activities, gather data from the web and directly observe operational projects. We will also interview Citizen Science experts and a broad range of current and former participants. Our outputs will include a community platform, recommendations, summaries, analyses, reviews and advisory notes.

Meet the project partnership, made up of researchers, managers and experts from:

- The Mofet Institute, Israel
- RIAS, Germany
- Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain
- Wissenschaftsladen Wien, Austria
- Universidad Pompeu Fabra, Spain
- University of Jyväskylä, Finland
- ATiT, Belgium
- FORTH, Greece
- Wissenschaft im Dialog, Germany

Follow our work via our project website: www.cstrack.eu

To know more about our work and to join our community, contact us via email: info@cstrack.eu

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